

CONTINUOUS AND COMPREHENSIVE EVALUATION: AN APPROACH OF NEW EVALUATION SYSTEM

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Abstract

Evaluation is indispensable part of education system. Our education system suffers from lot of imperfection in evaluation of students since independence, lots of commissions and policies recommended a new evaluation scheme for evaluation, which is child centered and caters the need and objectives of education. For improving the quality of education through reform Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation came out as a powerful tool for providing quality of education to the learner which ultimately leads to well skilled qualified learner. Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation proposed by central board of secondary education (CBSE) in affiliated schools for holistic development of students at all stage. This paper is an attempt to give brief idea about the researches has been done for Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation and what are the perspectives prevailing in the society for Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation.

Key words: Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation, Evaluation, examination reform, challenges, perception, attitude.

Introduction:

The achievement and quality of any student is based on the evaluation system, how evaluation is carried out in our education system. According to Henna “evaluation is the process of gathering and interpreting evidence on change in the behavior of all students as they progress through school”. in the educational context, evaluation implies broad programme then the examination, in which achievements, attitude, interests, personality traits and skills factors are taken into consideration. Thus cognitive, affective and psychomotor learning outcomes are measured in evaluation process. Based on the recommendations of examination reforms by NCF 2005, CBSE has launched the new pattern of evaluation system i.e., continuous and comprehensive evaluation which focuses on multiple abilities of children in totality. Therefore the teachers’ role and responsibilities have been magnified to perform classroom activities and continuously evaluate children from various angles.

Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation (CCE) introduce with a broad minded concept of providing wider scope to student to utilize their inherent talent to achieve their desired goal. Its ultimate aim is to reduce stress and anxiety which students often face before and after examination. This new system of evaluation tests the skills of a child in such a way to give the correct picture of their behavior, abilities, interest and talent of the child. This can be done by the only teacher who is ultimately pivoted of the educational system and the same time improves the quality of education.

Characteristics of Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation

- It is informal and formative in nature.
- It caters all aspect of development of the child according to their needs.
- It is based on assumption that teachers know their student very much therefore teacher only be charged with the responsibility of evaluation of their students.
- It provides the opportunity to teachers for the use multiple techniques for evaluation such as interview, observation, oral and also written presentation.
- It involves analysis and interpretation of the record of students achievements to arrive at right decision.

Different commissions and policies view on Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation

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Secondary Education Commission(Mudaliar Commission1964-66) “In order to find out the pupils all round progress and to determine his future, a proper system of school records should be maintained for every pupil indicating a work done by him from time to time and his attainments in the different spheres”.

Kothari Education Commission (1964-66) clearly states that in addition to all that is evaluated through the external examination school should also evaluate the other competencies of students. It suggested that the assessment should be comprehensive covering personality traits, interests and attitudes etc.

National Policy of Education (1968) envisaged for “combining external and internal assessment to form a certificate of performance spread over the total span of instructional time”. This idea is also reflects in National Policy on education (1986) in the form of Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation. Further it has been seen in the National Curriculum Framework for Secondary Education (NCFSE 2000) that evaluation must facilitate all round development of students. It states that school based evaluation will be in the form of Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation; it will incorporate assessment of not only the scholastic areas of students growth but also the non-scholastic areas.

According to National Curriculum Framework (NCF 2005) a good evaluation and examination system can become an integral part of the learning process and benefit both the learner’s themselves and the educational system by giving credible feedback.

National focus group (2005) on examination reforms also suggested that a school based evaluation system should be established in order to; reduce stress on children, make evaluation comprehensive and regular, provide space for the teacher for creative teaching and provides a tool for diagnosis and for producing learners with greater skills.

All the commissions advocated for reducing emphasis on external examination and encouraging internal assessment through continuous and comprehensive evaluation.

Many defects are present in the past system of evaluation which is examination centered not learners centered and it does not caters holistic development of the students and due to this our education system which does not provide quality of education. Many recommendations has been given in support of examination reform and thus Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation is came out which focuses to provide systematic pattern of evaluation by which student nourishes their talent. For any policy or scheme the biggest challenge is to implement it in such a manner that it achieves their desire goals or objectives behind the scheme. CBSE and NCERT did many efforts in implementing Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation in schools by providing teaching –learning materials which are appropriate for students with respect to their age, class and subject and at the same time provide continuous feedback to all the stakeholders to implement Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation in effective manner.

.REVIEW OF LITERATURE

The review of literature in the present study has been categorized into following sub headings.

- I. Concept of Continuous Comprehensive Evaluation
- II. Attitude and perception of teachers, parents and students toward Continuous Comprehensive Evaluation
- III. Challenges and effectiveness of Continuous Comprehensive Evaluation

Concept of Continuous Comprehensive Evaluation

Masih& Hussain (2013), discussed the system of Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation implemented by CBSE in the schools, with respect to constructivist approach of learning which is essential for student to construct knowledge instead of just acquiring it and this opportunity provided through new evaluation system i.e. Continuous

and Comprehensive Evaluation and also the role of teacher for effective implantation of this scheme who play crucial and active role in imparting knowledge in the learner.

Stella (2013) addressed the role of teacher in the present scenario of examination and evaluation. He discussed the role of teacher, functions and preparation in classroom transaction and in evaluation process with reference to Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation, how Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation help teacher in classroom, barriers of Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation and strategies for teacher to help in implementing Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation.

Monika (2013) investigated the concept of Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation, its importance, challenges in its implementation and suggest some probable solutions to overcome from the challenges and promote holistic learning.

Singh & Kumar (2013) investigated the concept of Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation, its need and importance, role of teachers and its implementation in school with an empirical support of studies which recommend holistic development through multiple tools and techniques.

Joshi (2013) examined the concept of Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation with reference to framework and its implementation at school level and revealed that the Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation are not exactly implemented as prescribed by framework. The findings are as same as the finding of Sonavane&Isave (2012).

Vembu (2013) in the paper entitled “Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation in CBSE schools” the focus of the paper was to indicate the importance, why Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation being adopted, advantages, implementation of Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation in schools and discussed the tools used for the evaluation. And also raised the point that in democratic schools it is essential to evaluate student? And student should decide themselves to measure their achievements.

Isav (2012) examined the concept of Continuous Comprehensive Evaluation with reference framework and its implementation at secondary level. Study concluded that: evaluation practices are carried out but not as mentioned as in framework, lack of record maintenance, lack of motivation in teachers to prepare their tools and acceptance of new system of evaluation.

Gupta & lata (2012) addressed the importance of school based assessment for holistic development of the learner by reducing stress and anxiety, resolve difficulties, give credible feedback, increase quality of learning, provide quality of performance, reduces memorisation and also provide choice based examination. The paper also raised the point that assessment system under Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation is very excellent to evaluate the educational objectives because it focuses on child centred, school centred and multi centred approaches which caters all round development of the students.

Singhal (2012) in the paper entitled “The journey of evaluation system from ancient gurukul to modern education system” reflects the rationale behind replacing the traditional examination system to new system of evaluation i.e. Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation and its relevance in schools. Further study revealed some problems/challenges associated with its execution and suggests remedial measures for its smooth execution.

Sharma &Behal (2012) discussed the importance of Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation which is emergence requirement for education in the present scenario, role of all stakeholders, its importance, characteristics, challenges and strategies for implementation of Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation.

Parkash& Kumar,(N.D) discussed the philosophical basis of Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation in keeping the view how the Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation is useful for the learner, importance, advantages and obstacle in Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation while implanting Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation in school.

Attitude and perception of teachers, parents and students toward Continuous Comprehensive Evaluation

Shandilya(2014) studied the perception perceived by secondary teachers towards the implementation of Continuous Comprehensive Evaluation with respect to their gender, designation, teaching experience and various dimensions of co-scholastic areas like life skills, attitude and values, co-curricular activities, physical and health education. She found there is an average level of favorable attitude towards implementation of Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation, also for co-scholastic areas and there is no significant difference found among teachers with respect to their gender and designation. Further the research revealed that teachers having lowest teaching experience had highest favorable attitude toward implementing Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation whereas teacher having highest teaching experience had low level of favorable attitude for Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation.

Ashita (2013) traced the current trends practice for educational assessment and studied the perception of teachers, students and parents towards Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation, its effects on instructions, equity concern and learning outcomes and challenges faced by the teachers in implementing Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation. The design of the intervention was based on the Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation package (forth coming) of NCERT. Analysis of class observations, informal interviews with the teachers indicate that though teachers were keen to implement Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation and enhance learning practice, but lacked understanding of implementation techniques and were concerned about the disruption to their teaching practices, and in particular about the freedom it gave to students in the classroom. The major findings were: (i) impact of Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation on teaching- learning is not good because it demands professional development of teachers, principals and administrators without which Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation remain superficial. (ii) There is a wide gap between marginalized and advantage group because of their less exposure to resources, their socio economic isolation which pertains inequality. Further the research revealed that challenges faced by the teachers in implementing Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation are: (i) greater student ratio, (ii) time consuming, (iii) irregulerness of students, (iv) Lack of resources and (v) inadequate training for implementation of Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation.

Badiyani (2013) studied the perception of teacher educators towards Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation and various strategies adopted by the teacher for evaluating students and found that the teacher perceives Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation with positive attitude and all are in favors of Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation but some points they point out is that they did not get proper time and adequate training for the implementation of Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation. The paper aims at answering two questions 1) what are the perceptions of teacher educators towards the Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation system? And 2) what are their recommendations about it? The study followed the design of a survey method and consisted a sample of Twenty five teacher educators from granted, grant-in aid and self-finance colleges affiliated to H.N.G.University. Data collection was done administering a questionnaire containing thirteen questions related to factors influencing internal assessment, the merits and demerits of the Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation and factors to be included or excluded from the Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation.

Singh, Patel & Desai (2013), studied the Attitude of Student Teachers towards Continuous Comprehensive Evaluation With Reference To Gender, Caste and Habitat from the sample 139 student teachers which comes from different profile like gender, caste and habitat and they found that there is a moderately favorable attitude for Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation among student teachers but there is no significant difference in attitude of student teacher with respect to their gender, caste and their habitat.

Kaut& Kaur (2013) studied the perception and attitude of teachers who belong from rural and urban background of jalandhar towards Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation at secondary level.100 teachers, 50 from rural and 50 from urban schools of CBSE schools were randomly selected. Scale of Attitude towards Continuous and

Comprehensive Evaluation and Scale of Perception towards Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation were administered by the researcher for the selected school teachers. and found that there is a significant difference between the perception of rural and urban teachers with respect to their performance, their personality and evaluation strategies adopted by them. Rural school teacher perceived Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation in better way while there is no significant difference in between their attitude towards Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation.

Lata (2013), studied the Perception of Teachers, Students and Parents regarding Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation at the Secondary Level. Her study revealed that teachers, parent and students were aware about the concept of Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation and knows the importance of Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation for the students. The teachers perceive Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation in right direction but the challenges they face to implement are lack of facilities, time.

Singhal (2012) her research is an attempt to find out teachers perception about the scheme of Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation and the problems they face while its execution and found that the perception of government school teachers is average which indicates moderate acceptability of Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation by teachers. Further the research revealed that the large number of students in classes, lack of appropriate training, inadequate infrastructure and teaching materials and increased volume of work act as barriers in smooth execution of Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation.

Srivastava, Bharti & Singh (2011), studied the perception of secondary school students towards Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation with respect to their classes, schools achievements and gender and also compare the perception of teacher and student, Incidental sampling technique was used to draw the sample of the study. Total sample size was 200 for students and 30 for teachers to CBSE public schools of Patna and found that student perceive Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation with positive manner and there is no significant difference in the perception of secondary students with respect to their gender, different school of Central Board of Secondary Education and their achievement. Further the research revealed that most of the teachers consider Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation as Burden and perceive Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation negatively.

Jaiswal (2010), studied the Attitude of teachers towards the new evaluation system i.e. Continuous Comprehensive Evaluation prevailing in primary and junior district board schools of Dadraul block of Shahjahanpur district with selected all the teachers of 20% of all the primary & junior schools he used self-made 5 point attitude scale to know the attitude of teachers towards Continuous Comprehensive Evaluation and found a significant difference between Para teachers and teachers with respect to their attitude towards the new system, and a remarkable difference is also found in the attitude of male and female teacher.

Challenges and effectiveness of Continuous Comprehensive Evaluation

Islam & Chakraborty (2012), made an attempt to assess the awareness level of in-service school teachers towards Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation with respect to their gender, demography and service experience in Murshidabad district of West Bengal, from the sample of 256 in-service secondary school teachers, which is selected from 8 different teaching institutions. They found there is a significant difference in awareness of student teachers toward Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation with respect to their gender but there is no significant difference is found among the student teacher toward Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation with respect to their demographic location and with their teaching experience.

Kothari & Thomas (2012), investigated the implementation status of Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation at upper primary level with respect to how Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation is implemented by the teachers, evaluation strategies adopted by the teacher for assessing scholastic and co-scholastic area and challenges faced by the teachers while implementing Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation, The study was carried out in

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Ernakulam district in the state of Kerala in 105 English medium schools and found that most of the teachers focus on scholastic aspect, there is a greater student ratio, discipline, inadequate training and material for teachers and heavy syllabus due to which teacher finds difficult to manage time while implementing Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation.

Sonawane & Isave (2012) addressed the problem/challenges of Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation at secondary schools of Marathi medium located in Pune district with the sample 30 school teachers selected by random sampling method. Purpose of his study is to examine the concept of Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation as per the viewpoints of framework and its implementation at school level from the sample of 30 secondary teachers. Major findings of the study were: (i) Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation is implemented in school but not as mentioned in the framework, (ii) Lack of maintenance of records and own evaluation tool, (iii) Feedback is not provided and remedial instruction are discussed only in PTA meeting or mentioned in the diary. (iv) Teacher feels the Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation scheme is hectic for them.

Jadal (2011), studied the effectiveness of Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation on students' attainments at primary level and found that attainment of any concept and development of multiple abilities/ or having mastery in skills can be achieved by the Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation at primary level, tools and techniques used in Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation scheme provides motivation, maximum exposure to enhance their skills and also help students in the acquisition of different performance. Further the research revealed that perfect planned evaluation has a profound impact on the learning.

Manjula & Purshotam (N.D) conducted a study entitled "Effectiveness of Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation over the evaluation practice of teachers". The main of the study was to study the impact of Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation at primary level, how teacher practices evaluation by using training packages. Major finding of the study were: evaluation should be school based which will incorporate holistic development, teacher should be well equipped with essential skills and competencies and should be trained so they would be able to integrate evaluation in their teaching learning process and fulfill the purpose of Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation

Conclusion

The review of literature shows that the various studies have been conducted in the field of evaluation. The social consequences of examination vis-à-vis evaluation system are of great significance and concern for students, parents, educational administrators, policy makers and in fact the society at large.

Some of the studies (Masih & Hussain, (2013), Stella, (2013), Monika (2013) Singh & Kumar (2013) Joshi (2013) Vembu (2013) Isav (2012) Gupta & Lata (2012) Singhal (2012) Sharma & Behal (2012) examined the concept of Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation and addressed the importance of this new Evaluation system and the same time stressed on the role of teacher in implementing Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation. Studies emphasized that the present evaluation system adopted in the schools is confined to scholastic areas which restricts the evaluation procedure to the testing of cognitive domain. Parkash & Kumar, (N.D) discussed the philosophical basis of Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation in keeping the view how the Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation is useful for the learner, importance, advantages and obstacle in Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation while implanting CCE in school.

Some of the studies Shandilya (2014) Ashita (2013) Badiyani (2013) Singh, Patel & Desai (2013), Kaut & Kaur (2013) Lata (2013), Singhal (2012), Jaiswal (2010) studied the perception of all stakeholders such as parents, teachers and students, teacher educators. All the stakeholders are in the favor of Continuous and Comprehensive

Evaluation and shows favorable attitude but one of the study revealed that Srivastava, Bharti & Singh (2011) Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation for teachers act as a burden and perceive Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation negatively. Some of the studies ShandilyaIslam &Chakraborty (2012),Kothari & Thomas (2012), studied the challenges faced by the teachers and educational stakeholders to implement the CCE in educational institute and schools. As we know the biggest challenge is to implement Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation in schools, all the studies pointed some challenges to implement it like: lack of facilities in schools, professional development of teachers to this new evaluation scheme, time constraint, lack of accountability of teachers, students ratio etc. Sonawane&Isave (2012) is one of the studies which revealed that Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation scheme is hectic for teachers because it demands multiple functional roles. Jadal (2011),Manjula&Purshotam (N.D) studied the effectiveness of Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation and found that Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation helps students for holistic development and further the research revealed that role of teacher is very important for proper implementation of Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation.

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